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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
BDIs	Blue Data Infrastructures
CCP	Cloud Container Platform
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
CNR	Italian National Research Council
DD&AS	Data Discovery & Access Service
D4Science Infrastructure	Data Infrastructure promoting Open Science (managed by CNR)
DIVAnd	Data interpolating variational analysis in n dimensions
DTO	Digital Twin Ocean

ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EMB	European Marine Board
EM	Exploitation Measure
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EO	Exploitation Objective
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOVs	Essential Ocean Variables
EU HFR	European High Frequency Radar Node
GRSF	Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries
HF	High-Frequency
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System
KER	Key Exploitable Result
MEI	Marine Environmental Indicators
MPA	Marine Protected Area
NRT	Near-Real-Time
OTGA	Ocean Teacher Global Academy
QA	Quality Assurance
QC	Quality Control
REA	European Research Executive Agency
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organisations
RI	Research Infrastructure
SSI	Enhanced Storm Severity
TBD	To Be Defined
TRIX	Trophic State Index
VLab	Virtual Laboratory
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WB	Workbench
WP	Working Package

Keywords

EOSC; Virtual Labs; Big Data; Virtual Research Environment; Data infrastructures

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The **EOOSC Node "European Digital Twin Ocean"** represents the next strategic step in the evolution of the open science ecosystem developed by the Horizon Europe "Blue-Cloud 2026" project (<https://blue-cloud.org>). Building on both the achievements of the Horizon 2020 "Blue-Cloud pilot" project and "**Blue-Cloud 2026**", this Strategic Roadmap outlines a long-term vision (2026–2035) and action plan for the exploitation and further development of Blue-Cloud's Key Exploitable Results as a marine thematic node within the **European Open Science Cloud (EOOSC)**, integrated with **EDITO**, the public infrastructure platform of the **European Digital Twin Ocean**.

The "Blue-Cloud 2026" project has delivered a suite of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) — including core and generic services, spatial and data management services, high-value thematic services, and training materials that, together, constitute an EOOSC-compliant open science ecosystem for marine and aquatic research. These KERs are documented in a Joint Exploitation Plan, which identifies objectives, targets, and exploitation activities for the period 2026–2028. Significant developments in the European marine knowledge landscape during the project implementation period (2023–2026) — including the evolution of EDITO, the establishment of the EOOSC Federation, and the launch of the European Ocean Pact — have signaled a clear opportunity for Blue-Cloud to evolve as an **EOOSC marine thematic node**. The new **EOOSC Node "European Digital Twin Ocean"** will champion a vision where major EU marine knowledge assets (i.e. EMODnet, Copernicus Marine, EDITO), and environmental and marine Research Infrastructures (from ESFRI and beyond) are central to driving marine data provision in EOOSC, supporting and catalysing open science developments in the marine and freshwater domains. The Node will:

- Ensure that the **EDITO** platform, catalogue and services (<https://www.edito.eu/>) are fully accessible and integrated within EOOSC, including by influencing EOOSC requirements to avoid unnecessary duplication of efforts by encouraging the adoption of international, open standards by the EOOSC Federation.
- Support scientists and researchers in designing, testing, and evaluating innovative computational analytical flows that extract valuable knowledge from diverse datasets, while accelerating open science and collaborative research in support of the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters".
- Offer a comprehensive environment for sharing data, tools, and knowledge, fostering a "web of scientific insight" that supports the federation of relevant marine and aquatic data sources for discovery by the entire EOOSC community, fostering their ingestion into EDITO (including via relevant, existing services i.e., EMODnet) towards nurturing and co-evolving the European Digital Twin Ocean.

The ambition is that by 2035, the EOOSC Node "European Digital Twin Ocean" is delivered as an operational service offered in the framework of the EDITO program, contributing to accelerate the co-creation and further expansion of the European Digital Twin Ocean by facilitating multidisciplinary research collaboration across EOOSC, and onboarding of valuable, community validated digital assets onto EDITO. Three distinctive phases are envisioned towards this end:

- **Phase 1 (Sep 2026 - Aug 2029):** Set up - from candidate to production.

- **Phase 2 (Sep 2029 - Dec 2030):** Operations at EOSC level.
- **Phase 3 (Jan 2031- Dec 2035):** Service Sustainability, Governance and Scale Up.

This Strategic Roadmap outlines the phases, objectives, expected results and Action Plan 2026-2028 required to make progress towards that goal, as well as offering recommendations to key stakeholders towards the successful delivery of the Node’s vision and mission. The Action Plan 2026-2028 will be rolled out through the action **“EOSC-Marine: Operationalizing the EOSC Node | European Digital Twin Ocean to Support the EU Mission Ocean & Waters”** (Horizon Europe project 101292903), funded by the European Research Executive Agency (REA).

Figure 1: Strategic Roadmap for the EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean”

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1 Background, scope and objective of this document

The Horizon Europe “**Blue-Cloud 2026**” project (<https://blue-cloud.org>) has further evolved the pilot, web-based open science ecosystem developed by the Horizon 2020 “**Blue-Cloud pilot**” project by upscaling it towards becoming a federated European marine thematic ecosystem, aiming to deliver FAIR and open data and analytical services into the **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)**. These services are intended to be instrumental for deepening research of the ocean, EU seas, coastal & inland waters in support of EU policy objectives, and specifically those of the EU Mission “**Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030**”¹, in particular delivering to the further development of the infrastructure of the European Digital Twin Ocean (EDITO) - the bedrock of the Mission. This evolution has been guided by the strategic guidelines set forth in the “**Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap to 2030**”², which outlined a **vision** and a strategic **action plan** towards evolving Blue-Cloud’s efforts beyond the “Blue-Cloud pilot” project.

During the “Blue-Cloud 2026” project, this evolution has led to the successful development of Key Exploitable Results (KERs), in line with the action plan mapped out in the Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap to 2030 (see Section 2). The Blue-Cloud 2026 project has evolved and delivered a number of KERs, namely: Blue-Cloud 2026 Virtual Research Environment; Blue-Cloud 2026 Core and Generic Services; Blue-Cloud 2026 Spatial & Data Management Services; Blue-Cloud 2026 High Value Thematic Services; and Blue-Cloud 2026 Training Courses & Materials. These KERs have been the subject of a Joint Exploitation Plan³ that identifies objectives, targets and exploitation activities for these results in the period 2026-2028, as a synergetic digital ecosystem encapsulated in the [Blue-Cloud platform](#), which is now EOSC compliant.

Building on the Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap to 2030 and the Joint Exploitation Plan, this document delivers the “**Strategic Roadmap Towards Building a Federated Digital Ecosystem in Support of the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean & Waters into EOSC**” (hereafter “Strategic Roadmap”). The Strategic Roadmap integrates the exploitation measures identified in the Joint Exploitation Plan into a long-term vision and strategy, as part of the desired **strategic pathway** for long-term exploitation and further evolution of this open science ecosystem as a **marine thematic node** within **EOSC**, and its integration into **EDITO**. It updates the Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap to 2030, delivering a longer-term approach (2026-2035) towards building a federated digital ecosystem into EOSC that contributes to both the co-creation of the European Digital Twin Ocean via community-driven innovation and to expose the EDITO assets, catalogue, and services to EOSC users, and vice versa.

Considering the results achieved so far (Section 2), and relevant developments in the European marine knowledge landscape during the project implementation (Section 3), this Strategic Roadmap outlines the added value (Section 4) that the marine thematic node should bring to the new emerging landscape and the vision for its delivery (Section 5), including setting strategic objectives and an action plan towards that end. It reflects on the pathways towards sustainability that will be followed to deliver the initial action plan and future phases (Section 6), and issues recommendations (Section 7) to key target audiences to support the successful delivery of the vision and mission of the EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean”.

¹ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/06b9b2a8-5ba5-11f0-a9d0-01aa75ed71a1>

² Vera, J., Larkin, K., Delaney, C., Tonné, N., Cisternino, S., Calewaert, J.-B., Pittonet, S., Drago, F., Schaap, D. M. A., Pagano, P., Obaton, D., Ellenbroek, A., Cabrera, P., & Drudi, M. (2022). Blue-Cloud D6.4 Strategic Roadmap (Release 2) (Versión 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10067460>

² Vera, J., Larkin, K., Delaney, C., Tonné, N., Cisternino, S., Calewaert, J.-B., Pittonet, S., Drago, F., Schaap, D. M. A., Pagano, P., Obaton, D., Ellenbroek, A., Cabrera, P., & Drudi, M. (2022). Blue-Cloud D6.4 Strategic Roadmap (Release 2) (Versión 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10067460>

³ Vera, J. (2026). Blue-Cloud 2026 - D7.3 Joint Exploitation Plan (Versión 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18189861>

2 Progress achieved in implementing the Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap to 2030

The Horizon Europe “Blue-Cloud 2026” project has followed the Action Plan mapped out in 2022 to guide its evolution in the period 2023-2026, fully delivering the expected assets and results (see figure 2).

All actions planned for 2023-2026 have been completed, with only two exceptions across the 5 Strategic Action Paths that structured the plan. The activities carried out have led to an expansion of both the federation of data into the DD&AS and the catalogue of VLabs and Workbenches available in the platform. The Training Academy has been successfully rolled out and the Digital Twin Ocean (DTO) Task Force established, critically facilitating progress towards the next phases of implementation.

Figure 2: Status of implementation of the Blue-Cloud (2022) Strategic Roadmap to 2030

There are only two activities that have not progressed as planned, namely the expansion of the DD&AS with freshwater repositories, and the engagement with the private sector to develop analytical services for Blue Economy applications. In these cases, lack of action has been due to conscious prioritization of other activities. On one hand, the expansion of the DD&AS with freshwater repositories has not been addressed as it has been agreed that such integration will rather be pursued by other existing, established marine data services (e.g., EMODnet), which will contribute to streamline and strengthen the marine

knowledge community, rather than overlapping or duplicating efforts. On the other hand, the engagement of the private sector in the development of digital twinning applications will be pursued in the next phase of the roadmap, which will open new avenues of opportunity for collaboration with Blue Economy actors, benefitting from a more mature and fit-for-purpose digital twinning environment thanks to alignment with EDITO, the public infrastructure of the European Digital Twin Ocean (see sections 3 and 4). The re-definition of these activities has not had an impact on the results achieved, nor will impede the further implementation of the roadmap.

3 The European marine knowledge landscape: Relevant developments and evolution 2023-2026

3.1 Key developments in the European marine knowledge landscape

The European marine knowledge value chain has undergone significant changes in recent years (2023-2026), progressing further on its evolution from a fragmented landscape into an integrated, policy-driven ecosystem fundamental to the European Union (EU) ocean governance. This evolution reflects Europe's recognition that robust marine data is not merely a scientific asset but a strategic foundation for addressing interconnected challenges spanning climate adaptation, biodiversity restoration, and sustainable blue economy development. Significant milestones in this evolution include:

- The **European Ocean Pact**: Launched in June 2025, it brings together the EU's policies and actions related to the ocean and creates a unified and coordinated plan for managing the ocean. The Pact positions marine knowledge as a cross-cutting foundation for EU policy implementation and will be complemented by an Ocean Act planned for 2027. As part of these efforts, the EC announced the launch of an operational "Ocean Observation Initiative", the "Ocean Eye", that will scale up European capabilities to coordinate in situ ocean observation and monitoring, supporting EU ocean technology and innovation, and positioning the EU as a global leader towards delivering a sustained global ocean observing system.
- The **European Digital Twin Ocean**: Announced by President von der Leyen at the One Ocean Summit in Brest in February 2022, this initiative has evolved significantly in 2022-2025 through the development of its core infrastructure, **EDITO** (<https://www.edito.eu>), which is built on data from **Copernicus Marine Service** and the **European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet)**, AI-driven ocean modelling, and pan-European scientific infrastructure. In 2025, the capabilities of EDITO were showcased at the United Nations Ocean Conference in Nice, France.
- **EMODnet evolution**: In January 2023, EMODnet (<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en>) took a bold step by transforming from seven distinct thematic portals into a single, unified web portal, with the unified portal welcoming 30% more visitors than all previous thematic sites combined. EMODnet now serves over 120,000 stakeholders annually and has expanded to include 133 organizations from 33 countries, and it is recognized as a cornerstone of European marine knowledge. In November 2025, EMODnet launched its Vision 2035. The EMODnet Vision 2035 is a common roadmap for EMODnet's service evolution over the next decade, responding to the

growing societal demand for marine knowledge and positioning EMODnet as a key service for the Ocean Pact and the EU Ocean Observation Initiative. The roadmap includes a phased approach:

- **Consolidate (2025-2027):** Consolidate and prepare to scale, strengthen trust and transparency, unify technical coordination, and enhance engagement.
 - **Scale (2028-2030):** Scale by expanding partnerships and data integration, maximising interoperability with the European Digital Twin Ocean by leveraging its core services, and enhanced integration of Member State policy data, expanded offer of coastal, deep ocean and polar domains.
 - **Transform (2031-2035):** Transform by operating at full potential, delivering a resilient, robust and sustained service providing maximum data integration, full interoperability and global leadership.
- **Copernicus Marine Service evolution:** Since 2023, the Copernicus Marine Service (<https://marine.copernicus.eu/>) has achieved significant progress in enhancing the accessibility, performance and usability of its data offer, supporting the broader evolution of the European marine knowledge ecosystem towards more integrated and user-oriented services. A key development has been the adoption of cloud-optimised data formats, notably ARCO (Analysis Ready Cloud Optimised), enabling more efficient data access, reduced latency, and improved scalability for users. This transformation has been instrumental in facilitating faster data discovery and retrieval, as well as enabling new types of applications based on large-scale data processing. These technical advancements have been underpinned by the deployment of the Marine Data Store, developed by Mercator Ocean International (MOi) with the objective of making Copernicus Marine data as accessible and performant as possible. The Marine Data Store represents a major step forward in providing unified, scalable and programmatic access to marine data, aligned with FAIR principles and the European Green Deal Data Space, in full compliance with the Copernicus programme. Together, these developments illustrate a shift towards a more performant, accessible and interoperable marine data service, reinforcing the role of Copernicus Marine as a cornerstone of the European marine knowledge value chain and its integration within EDITO, EOSC and the wider European data ecosystem.

The marine knowledge value chain has further been strengthened through alignment with the **EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters** and integration with **Horizon Europe** funding programs. In addition, a significant development has been the launch of the **European Green Deal Data Space**, which is one of the Common European Data Spaces envisioned by the European Commission (EC). The Green Deal Data Space is conceived as a digital ecosystem to enable secure, trusted sharing, exchange and re-use of environmental and sustainability-related data across the EU — covering biodiversity, climate change, pollution, circular economy, and other Green Deal priorities. The goal is to make high-value data **FAIR** (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) to support its reuse for policymaking, innovation, research, and private-sector services in line with the European Green Deal’s objectives⁴. Other relevant developments include the recent launch of the **EIT Water Knowledge and Innovation Community**, a new KIC in the field of water, marine and maritime sectors and ecosystems, which is expected to address fragmentation and skills gaps across the water-marine-maritime sectors.

⁴ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/law-and-governance/green-data_en

European Research Infrastructures (RIs) also play a crucial role in the European marine knowledge landscape, strengthening Europe’s ability to produce new knowledge and innovation. The **European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI)** has helped shape the research landscape in Europe through the identification, development, connectivity and support of new and existing RIs. ESFRI’s goal is to strengthen European research, providing the tools needed to address scientific, societal and economic challenges. ESFRI analyses the European landscape of RIs and maintains a Roadmap for the implementation and monitoring of a strong infrastructure base. To date, the ESFRI Roadmap has enabled the design and development of 55 strategic RIs, mobilising almost € 20 billion of investments across the EU. To this end, Europe now has one of the most advanced and integrated Research Infrastructure systems in the world, which is a cornerstone in the development of the **European Research Area**. European RIs foster the definition, implementation and further development of advanced solutions for the effective provisioning and use of high-quality scientific data, with effective metadata descriptors, ease of access, interoperability and reusability, fully implementing the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles. These efforts are recognized and also utilised to contribute to shaping the European Open Science Cloud. In practice, RIs are essential for the implementation of EOSC as they bring together and give access to high-quality multidisciplinary scientific data and engage scientific communities, acting both as providers and users. For that reason, there is major synergy between the ESFRI activities and the EOSC implementation. In the marine domain there are several RIs which have been included in the ESFRI Roadmap, such as e.g. Euro-Argo, EMSO, ICOS-Marine, SIOS, EMBRC, ELIXIR, each focusing on collecting and analysing specific in-situ observations. In addition, there is SeaDataNet as a leading RI for marine and ocean data management, and EurOBIS as leading RI for marine biodiversity data management.

The current landscape and related developments aim towards a fundamental shift from fragmented, national-level marine data systems toward an integrated, EU-wide marine knowledge ecosystem that increasingly takes a more holistic “source to sink” approach to our marine, coastal and inland waters as enshrined in the Mission, designed to support evidence-based policy, blue economy innovation, and ocean restoration efforts. The marine knowledge value chain now explicitly supports:

- The **Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)**, which is currently under review, following the Water Resilience Strategy and European Ocean Pact announcements.
- The **Maritime Spatial Planning Directive**, which is being evaluated and will be revised as part of the Ocean Pact.
- The **Nature Restoration Law**, which has been formally adopted by the European Parliament and the Council of the EU and is in force as Regulation (EU) 2024/1991.
- The **Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ) Agreement**, which reached 60 ratifications and entered into force on 17 January 2026.

Parallel with these developments, significant progress has been achieved by flagship initiatives launched to advance open science and digital innovation in Europe, namely the **European Open Science Cloud**. **EOSC** is an initiative to create a federated, open, and multi-disciplinary digital environment for European researchers, academics, innovators, and citizen scientists. It aims to provide researchers and innovators in Europe with an open and trusted multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and reuse

data, tools and services for research and innovation. It is built around the FAIR data principles and serves as the common European research and innovation data space⁵.

EOSC is the tangible outcome of a number of key European and global policy milestones and position statements regarding Open Science. It is an integral part of, and supports, the European Commission’s strategy for realising the European Research Area (ERA), in particular the policy priorities of Open Innovation, Open Science and Open to the World and the goal of advancing FAIR data. In 2024, EOSC took an important leap forward with the launch of the EOSC EU Node. In 2025, the EOSC EU Node released its open-source code publicly, reinforcing transparency and knowledge transfer enabling other nodes to reuse components. In parallel, the EOSC Federation entered its build-up phase, announcing the set-up of multiple thematic and regional EOSC Nodes and opening a process to receive proposals for candidate nodes to enroll (see Figure 3).

The EOSC Federation will consist of multiple EOSC Nodes that are interconnected and can collaborate to share and manage scientific data, knowledge, and resources within and across thematic and geographical research communities.

The EOSC Nodes will be entry points for users to the EOSC Federation, with each node offering its own and possibly third-party services, including data reposing and accessing services.

As the decision-making body for EOSC, the EOSC Tripartite Governance oversees the structure, governance and operations of the EOSC Federation.

More info on the [EOSC website](#).

Figure 3: Status Building the EOSC federation: vision from the EOSC Tripartite group, October 2024

3.2 Opportunity for added value in the wake of these developments

Developments in the marine knowledge value chain, coupled with progress achieved in the evolution of the Blue-Cloud open science ecosystem and the experience built in ensuring interoperability with the EOSC Federation, have signaled an opportunity for Blue-Cloud to evolve as an **EOSC marine thematic node**. Such an evolution will not only contribute to the further buildup of EOSC with a well-organized community focusing on marine and aquatic research, but also to supporting current developments in the marine knowledge value chain in Europe by contributing to expand the reach of existing flagship initiatives (EMODnet, Copernicus Marine, EDITO) with new data products, services and/or applications, and to bridging them to EOSC, thereby opening opportunities to increase their exposure to multidisciplinary research communities, and to further advance science in the marine domain in support of environmental, economic, and societal objectives. Important considerations in the pursuit of this opportunity are the recommendations received from stakeholders consulted⁶ during the Blue-Cloud 2026 project as part of a “roadmap consultation”, which indicated that the Blue-Cloud 2026 assets and results should aim to *“integrate with major landscape developments to find consolidation into a single solution that can service*

⁵ <https://eosc.eu>

⁶ MS.34 – Key Roadmap recommendations from stakeholder consultation, use cases and ESEB (Vera J., Calewaert JB., McMeel O., 2025 - <https://data.d4science.net/2b2vz/>)

the marine science community. The community needs one single ecosystem that researchers can access without needing to understand the landscape, nor know the name of service providers”. And to “keep scientists in the driver seat: developments should not be technology driven, but user demand driven”.

The proposed EOSC marine thematic node will play a key role in unifying the above-described existing digital ecosystems (EOSC, EDITO), ensuring that these strategic pillars of (marine) research are technically and operationally connected, towards preventing new, larger silos between **EDITO** -the core infrastructure of the **European Digital Twin Ocean**- and the long-tail scientific community, reducing confusion for users and delivering to their needs and expectations. The new EOSC node will act as a strategic and operational bridge, promoting dedicated mechanisms to federate marine research capacity into the EOSC ecosystem. Becoming a node of the EOSC Federation will bring further benefits to the marine knowledge community. For example, the collaborative approach of the Federation will enable the availability of additional computing resources to manage peak demand from users e.g., when training and/or executing digital twin models and applications, which require considerable resources.

In addition, the evolution of the Blue-Cloud open science ecosystem as a marine thematic EOSC node will deliver other direct benefits, including enhancing scientific productivity and shortening the time that researchers invest in transforming research outputs into actionable information, by specifically:

- **Easing the transformation of marine data to new knowledge and specific products, towards expanding the data lake of the European Digital Twin Ocean:** The node will service and support marine data scientists aiming at harmonising heterogeneous data sets from different marine data infrastructures and Research Infrastructures, enabling generation and deepening of scientific knowledge, and potentially faster production of new data sets and/or products that can be ingested in existing European marine data services (i.e., Copernicus Marine, EMODnet) for publication and reusability by other users, including via the EDITO platform to co-create the European Digital Twin Ocean.
- **Facilitating multidisciplinary research collaboration to co-create the European Digital Twin Ocean:** The node will contribute to building collaboration with other EOSC nodes that have digital assets (e.g., environmental data, socioeconomic data) of potential value for the marine community, with a view of contributing to the further build-up of the European Digital Twin Ocean via the EDITO platform and expanding its user community.
- **Inspiring and accelerating community-driven innovation:** The node will enable the application of open science practices allowing users to reuse and reproduce data, methods, models and applications developed by the node community, contributing to accelerate innovation around solutions to ocean challenges. Direct interoperability of the node with EDITO will enable resulting innovations to be harnessed by societal stakeholders via the European Digital Twin Ocean.
- **Strengthening EDITO with additional resources contributing to infrastructure robustness:** The node will provide a trusted, secure, and scalable environment for scientific computation and collaboration through Virtual Labs and interoperable workflows, further enhancing EDITO’s infrastructure capabilities while ensuring its compliance and interoperability with EOSC.

4 Building a federated digital ecosystem in support of Mission “Ocean & Waters” into EOSC

4.1 Blue-Cloud re-positioning as a thematic marine node for EOSC

In 2025, following extensive exchanges with the EOSC Association, CNR-ISTI, on behalf of the Blue-Cloud 2026 consortium, put forward an application for Blue-Cloud to become a marine thematic EOSC node. The proposals from Blue-Cloud 2026, and those of twelve additional national and thematic candidate nodes were accepted by the EOSC Association as part of the ‘first wave’ of EOSC nodes. In consultation with European Commission (EC) stakeholders, Blue-Cloud 2026 consortium Partners have decided to continue as a candidate node under the name “**EOSC Node European Digital Twin Ocean**”.

A major goal and purpose of the **EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean”** will be to connect and expose the **EDITO** infrastructure and its resources to **EOSC**. The Node will provide a discovery and access service component of EDITO into the EOSC ecosystem, thereby delivering EDITO FAIR open data and analytical services to the EOSC Federation. The Node will enhance the EOSC ecosystem further by giving access to the flexible and user-friendly EDITO platform (<https://www.edito.eu>) for data-intensive applications and reproducible workflows. EDITO is the official (EC) hub for digital twins and components co-creating the **European Digital Twin Ocean**. As part of its strategic roadmap (see Section 5), the Node will work to transition from a candidate node to a fully operational, federated thematic node (achieving TRL 9), ensuring compliance with EOSC Federation rules, providing quality service, and implementing a long-term sustainability plan within the EDITO framework (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: General vision for the EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean”

The **EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean”** will aim to provide additional added value to EDITO by further positioning itself as a state-of-the-art cyberspace designed to incubate new research ideas in EOSC. Functioning as a “factory” for marine science, the node will support scientists and researchers in designing, testing, and evaluating innovative computational analytical flows that extract valuable knowledge from diverse datasets, while accelerating open science and collaborative research in support of the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters”. Managed by CNR and powered by the D4Science e-infrastructure, the Node leverages EOSC Core capabilities—including Authentication, Authorisation and Accounting (AAI), monitoring, and a helpdesk—to optimise the user experience and support efficient collaboration.

The node will offer a comprehensive environment for sharing data, tools, and knowledge, fostering a "web of scientific insight" that creates a federation of relevant marine and aquatic data sources for the entire EOSC community. By integrating advanced analytical tools, robust computing resources, and diverse datasets from marine observations and models, the node will empower researchers to tackle complex ocean challenges and will enhance the scientific community's ability to understand and predict marine phenomena. Beyond those services offered by **EDITO**, the node will offer a suite of common services and tools, including additional cloud storage and processing capabilities, and **Galaxy**, alongside a specialised Software Importer. These tools empower researchers to create and manage **Virtual Laboratories (VLabs)** and **Thematic Services**, facilitating seamless collaboration by enabling the efficient sharing of research artefacts.

4.2 Contribution of the marine thematic EOSC node to EDITO, Copernicus Marine and EMODnet

As the node strives to bring added value to the existing European marine knowledge landscape, it is of crucial importance that its role is clearly scoped, to avoid duplication and overlap, or to avoid contributing to more confusion or frustration in the landscape for users and contributors. It must also not compete with existing European capabilities (i.e., Copernicus Marine, EMODnet, EDITO). These recommendations stemmed from stakeholder consultations⁷, indicating that the node should:

- **Contribute to strengthen and not fragment existing European marine knowledge services, community and value chain:** As the results of Blue-Cloud 2026 are exploited to build the EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean”, the Blue-Cloud 2026 Consortium should be mindful that neither the project-based Blue-Cloud infrastructure (D4Science) and/or services nor those offered by the new node should be seen as aiming to compete, substitute, or undermine existing long-term European services (namely, Copernicus Marine Service, EMODnet and EDITO). The future exploitation and further development of Blue-Cloud 2026’s Key Exploitable Results should be geared at enhancing and strengthening these services, via federation of D4Science with EDITO.
- **Communicate a clear vision to external audiences:** The Blue-Cloud 2026 Consortium is advised to ensure that any external communications should contribute to clarify and not confuse the marine knowledge community with regard to the intended direction of the node, which is to contribute to bridging EDITO and EOSC, ensuring a unified, single environment servicing users. If

⁷ Vera J., Calewaert J-B., McMeel O. (2025). MS.34: Key Roadmap recommendations from stakeholder consultation, use cases and ESEB. <https://data.d4science.net/2b2vZ>

the node aspires to achieve sustainability via EC funding, it must ensure that the community is not led to believe that the node is a separate infrastructure with autonomy to act independently of EDITO developments but rather is established to complement and contribute to the latter. It is in service of EDITO.

- **Implement open-source technologies to avoid vendor lock-in:** While new technologies developed and/or further evolved under Blue-Cloud 2026 are welcome as a positive by-product of research and innovation efforts, highlighting/including any proprietary technologies as key, integrated components of the node public infrastructure should be avoided, ensuring that its nature as an open, public service can be secured at all times. This means that the EOSC node should be driven by open-source technologies.

The node **will**:

- Expose EDITO’s services to EOSC users.
- Develop new EOSC services and products in a way that allows easy adoption in the EDITO environment.
- Foster ingestion of new data into EDITO via existing services (i.e., EMODnet, Copernicus Marine), to allow new product creation by EDITO users.
- With a view to the sustainability of the EOSC node, develop an outlook for EOSC that supports the permanent pillars of the marine data landscape, namely EMODnet, Copernicus Marine Service and EDITO.
- Ensure other thematics of EOSC (e.g., freshwater, atmospheric) are aware of the existence of this marine node, to maximise trans-disciplinary science and maximise awareness about EDITO.
- Promote clarity for the community, in collaboration with EDITO: It should be made clear that the node is not “another” digital twin of the ocean. Rather, the node is a marine ‘hub’ for EOSC and the data component is the EDITO data lake, which is served by EU’s marine data services EMODnet and Copernicus Marine.

The node will constructively work with the EOSC and marine knowledge communities to avoid:

- **Creating artificial, unnecessary barriers/funnels for in situ data.** The data pipeline should be such that all relevant *in situ* data are submitted to EMODnet (i.e., not to the EOSC Node). There currently are multiple pathways to EMODnet: e.g., Research Infrastructure data service may be harvested directly to EMODnet; a project and/or data collector can submit data to the relevant National Oceanographic Data Centre or to other relevant national ocean data assembly centre which then channels it to EMODnet. In specific cases, data that has no established pipeline in EMODnet (e.g., corporate data or citizen science data) can be submitted directly to EMODnet Data Ingestion service, until an alternative operational pipeline is established. Finally, data that does not fit in EMODnet can be submitted to EDITO, which is currently developing a data quality assurance process to facilitate data sharing and assimilation.
- **Developing strategies in isolation.** Beyond participation to the EOSC Federation, the node will be built on a strong, well-articulated connection between the EOSC node “European Digital Twin Ocean” and EDITO and engage with the wider marine knowledge community to co-design its further evolution.

In summary, the node will seek to complement and contribute to EDITO by:

- Acting as a bridge that makes the EDITO platform fully accessible and integrated within EOSC, without adding any unnecessary interface layers that might prevent EDITO from connecting to other EOSC nodes directly or vice versa, but rather supporting such direct interoperability, if/as needed.
- Presenting itself as the EOSC-facing research and collaboration component of EDITO that enables the wider ecosystem of the European Digital Twin Ocean to operate according to (EOSC related) open science principles. The node’s role is to ensure that EDITO’s services are not only discoverable in EOSC, but also fully EOSC-compliant.

This complementarity will be achieved through the application of two core operational principles:

- **Smart Federation:** Implementing a policy-driven, intelligent, and scalable connection to EDITO services and data (i.e., Copernicus Marine and EMODnet), ensuring resources are brought into EOSC where and when they are needed.
- **Radical Transparency:** Providing full, open access to policies, metadata, and processes governing the data and services, ensuring trust and traceability in all scientific activities performed within the node.

5 EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean”: Vision, mission, objectives and action plan 2026-2029

5.1 Vision for the EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean”

As introduced in previous sections, the Blue-Cloud 2026 Consortium has identified⁸ a **strategic pathway** for the exploitation of its open science ecosystem as a **marine and aquatic thematic node** within EOSC (namely, as the EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean”).

Ambition

To consolidate a marine thematic node in EOSC, establishing the technical and governance conditions that will guide the transition towards becoming a core component of the EDITO public infrastructure platform of the European Digital Twin Ocean.

This pathway has led to revisiting the Blue-Cloud Vision 2030⁹, reflecting on the opportunity of adapting and contributing to these developments. The EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean” will champion a vision where major EU marine knowledge assets (i.e. EMODnet, Copernicus Marine, EDITO), and environmental and marine Research Infrastructures (from ESFRI and beyond) are central to driving marine

⁸ Vera, J. (2026). Blue-Cloud 2026 - D7.3 Joint Exploitation Plan (Versión 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18189861>

⁹ Vera, J., Larkin, K., Delaney, C., Tonné, N., Cisternino, S., Calewaert, J.-B., Pittonet, S., Drago, F., Schaap, D. M. A., Pagano, P., Obaton, D., Ellenbroek, A., Cabrera, P., & Drudi, M. (2022). Blue-Cloud D6.4 Strategic Roadmap (Release 2) (Versión 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10067460>

data provision in EOSC, supporting and catalysing open science developments in the marine and freshwater domains.

Vision for the EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean” (formerly Blue-Cloud)

The EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean” will champion a vision where major EU marine knowledge assets (i.e. EMODnet, Copernicus Marine, EDITO), and environmental and marine Research Infrastructures (from ESFRI and beyond) are central to driving marine data provision in EOSC, supporting and catalysing open science developments in the marine and freshwater domains.

5.2 Mission of the EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean”

To deliver its vision, the EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean” will be set up and evolved with a mission to:

- Ensure that the **EDITO** platform, catalogue and services (<https://www.edito.eu/>) are fully accessible and integrated within EOSC, including by influencing EOSC requirements to avoid unnecessary duplication of efforts by encouraging the adoption of international, open standards by the EOSC Federation.
- Support scientists and researchers in designing, testing, and evaluating innovative computational analytical flows that extract valuable knowledge from diverse datasets, while accelerating open science and collaborative research in support of the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters”.
- Offer a comprehensive environment for sharing data, tools, and knowledge, fostering a "web of scientific insight" that supports the federation of relevant marine and aquatic data sources for discovery by the entire EOSC community, fostering their ingestion into EDITO (including via relevant, existing services i.e., EMODnet) towards nurturing and co-evolving the European Digital Twin Ocean.

5.3 Strategic objectives

Within its overall vision and mission, the following implementation **Phases**, **Strategic Objectives** (SO) and **Expected Outcomes** are envisioned (see Table 1):

Table 1: EOSC Node European Digital Twin Ocean implementation phases and strategic objectives

Phase	Period	Strategic Objective	Expected outcomes
1. Set up (from candidate to production)	Sep 2026- Aug 2029	To set up and evolve the candidate node as a functional thematic EOSC node for marine research, compliant with EOSC minimal node requirements as defined by the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC-IF), operating robust, state-of-the-art	An EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean” that is fully interoperable with EDITO and EOSC. Clarity amongst the user community as to the role of

		marine-focused Core and Generic Capabilities, based on evolved specifications across governance, operations, sustainability and technical interoperability with EDITO and EOSC.	the EOSC node as a core component of EDITO.
2. Operations at EOSC level	Sep 2029- Dec 2030	Based on outcomes and recommendations from Phase 1, deliver the node as an operational EOSC service. Discuss and agree on a governance scheme that aligns with the EOSC governance structures and that will ensure full integration of the node within the EDITO governance structure.	An operational EOSC node “European Digital Twin Ocean” offered as a service to EOSC users. A Governance Scheme for continued and effective technical collaboration of the EOSC marine thematic node as part of the EDITO infrastructure and with the EOSC governance structure.
3. Service Sustainability, Governance and Scale Up	2031-2035	To deliver the EOSC thematic node as an operational service offered in the framework of the EDITO program, allowing for effective scale-up of the node through wide stakeholder engagement and onboarding.	An operational service that accelerates the co-creation and further expansion of the European Digital Twin Ocean by facilitating multidisciplinary research collaboration across EOSC and onboarding of valuable, community validated digital assets onto EDITO. Wider user and stakeholder engagement.

5.4 Action Plan 2026-2029

As described in the previous section, the delivery of the vision for the EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean” has been staged in three phases (Set Up; Operations at EOSC Level; Service Sustainability, Governance & Scale Up). This Action Plan is designed to structure and guide the roll-out of those activities that are considered critical to make progress towards achieving the **strategic objective** set out for Phase 1 (Set Up - from Candidate to Production) in the period **2026-2029**. The roll out of Phase 2 (Operations at EOSC Level) and Phase 3 (Service Sustainability, Governance & Scale Up) will require specific action plans, based on the results achieved and recommendations emerging from the implementation of Phase 1.

This Action Plan is consistent with the **5 strategic paths of action** identified in the Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap to 2030¹⁰ as described below, adapted to new developments:

- **Strategic Action Path +CLOUD&IT:** (Further) Federate with key marine data, research and e-infrastructures and strategic initiatives (e.g., EOSC, EDITO) to enhance value to users.
- **Strategic Action Path +FAIR:** Sustain the flow of FAIR & open marine data into the new EOSC marine thematic node and harness the node to make new (marine, multidisciplinary) FAIR data available into core European services (EMODnet, Copernicus Marine, EDITO), as appropriate.
- **Strategic Action Path +APPLICATIONS:** Trigger the development of innovative data analytics methods around priority environmental challenges and opportunities thematically to inspire and guide the community towards further evolving applications in support of key policy objectives.
- **Strategic Action Path +COMMUNITY:** (Further) Grow a thriving ocean open science community able to navigate the landscape, and leveraging skills, incentives and rewards and promoting wide dissemination of FAIR methods and knowledge sharing incubated in the new EOSC marine thematic node to boost innovation at a wider scale.
- **Strategic Action Path +ALLIANCES:** Connect and align with wider developments and other communities to contribute to a European and a global, international knowledge system in support of the Ocean Pact, the EU Green Deal and the UN Agenda 2030.

These **strategic paths of action** are still applicable and will continue to guide action going forward, being instrumental in structuring an **Action Plan 2026-2029** towards the delivery of the Strategic Objective envisioned for the Set Up phase of the EOSC marine thematic node, as described in Table 2.

Table 2: Action Plan 2026-2029 in support of Strategic Objective 1

Strategic Objective 2026-2028: To set up and evolve the candidate node as a functional thematic EOSC node for marine research, compliant with EOSC minimal node requirements as defined by the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC-IF), operating robust, state-of-the-art marine-focused Core and Generic Capabilities, based on evolved specifications across governance, operations, sustainability and technical interoperability with EDITO and EOSC.			
Strategic Action Path +CLOUD&IT: (Further) Federate with key marine data, research and e-infrastructures and strategic initiatives (e.g., EOSC, EDITO) to enhance value to users.			
What	Who	When	KPI
A1. Develop and establish a smart federation and interoperability of the Virtual Research Environment of D4Science with EDITO			

¹⁰ Vera, J., Larkin, K., Delaney, C., Tonné, N., Cisternino, S., Calewaert, J.-B., Pittonet, S., Drago, F., Schaap, D. M. A., Pagano, P., Obaton, D., Ellenbroek, A., Cabrera, P., & Drudi, M. (2022). Blue-Cloud D6.4 Strategic Roadmap (Release 2) (Versión 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10067460>

Achieve identity federation with EDITO	CNR, MOI	By June 2026	Identity federation of D4Science with EDITO established: A common Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) to enable single sign-on between D4Science VREs and EDITO assets.
Cross-Node Service Interoperability	CNR, MOI	By June 2026	Adopt and implement the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EIF) guidelines to achieve full service-profile interoperability with EDITO. This includes the adoption of the EOSC Resource Profile v3.0 for all analytical services and processes.
Provide a clear set of policies, technical interfaces and governance guidelines that define the interoperability framework and smart federation model of the node, as part of the EDITO infrastructure	CNR, MOI, VLIZ, Ifremer, OGS, SSBE	By Dec 2027	Interoperability framework for federation of D4Science with EDITO defined
Define a timeline and key milestones for the full implementation of the interoperability framework	CNR, MOI, VLIZ, Ifremer, OGS, SSBE	By June 2028	Technical implementation roadmap for the interoperability framework defined
A2. Align the e-infrastructure of the EOSC marine thematic node with the EOSC EU Node reference architecture			
Bring the candidate node to production level	CNR, EOSC	By June 2026	EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean” in production level, according to EOSC Federation rules. This includes the integration of federated AAI with the EOSC EU Node (EEN)

			IAM and the synchronization of service monitoring and accounting with EOSC-Core.
EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean” enrollment in EOSC	CNR, EOSC	By July 2026	Submit the formal application for the European DTO Node to join the EOSC Federation, and assign key roles such as the Node Operation Manager and Cybersecurity Officer.
EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean” core capability alignment	CNR, EOSC	By Sept 2026	Integrate Node-level functions—including monitoring, accounting, and helpdesk systems—with the EOSC EU Node's federating capabilities.
EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean” catalogue integration	CNR, EOSC	By Oct 2026	Achieve full harvesting and synchronization of the European DTO Service Catalogue into the EOSC Resource Knowledge Graph (RKG) . This requires all resource metadata to be DCAT-AP compliant to ensure deduplication and high-fidelity discovery within the EOSC EU Node Resource Hub.
Compliance with reference architecture	CNR, EOSC	By Feb 2027	Map the Node's digital infrastructure to the mandatory "EOSC Node Reference Architecture" to ensure high-quality service delivery within the Federation.
Provide a clear set of policies, technical interfaces and governance guidelines that define the interoperability framework and smart federation model of the marine thematic node and of EDITO	CNR, MOi, EGI, Netfarm, Nubisware	By June 2028	Interoperability framework for federation of EDITO (and of the EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean” node as a component thereof) with EOSC defined

with EOSC, as part the EOSC Federation			
A3. Integrate Artificial Intelligence capabilities within the EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean”			
Deploy AI/ML environments within the VRE enabling model development and experimentation, and implement ocean intelligence services (recognition, anomaly detection, predictive modelling).	CNR	By Dec 2027	AI development environments deployed. AI-enabled services available through the node.
Enable natural language discovery. Integrate LLM services over marine datasets and DTO outputs.	CNR	By June 2028	LLM-powered assistant deployed
AI-assisted workflow composition. Develop an assistant to generate, adapt, and execute analysis workflows from natural-language prompts.	CNR	By Dec 2028	Reduction in pipeline development time Users adopting AI-assisted workflows
Trustworthy, reusable AI ecosystem. Create a repository of FAIR AI models and workflows with versioning and documentation, including guidelines aligned with EU Trustworthy AI (provenance, reproducibility, evaluation).	CNR	By Aug 2029	AI models /workflows shared in the repository. AI services compliant with guidelines
Strategic Action Path +FAIR: Sustain the flow of FAIR & open marine data into the new EOSC node and harness the node to make new (marine, multidisciplinary) FAIR data available into core European services (EMODnet, Copernicus Marine, EDITO), as appropriate.			
What	Who	When	KPI

<p>A4. Develop and establish FAIR & federated marine data services as part of the EOSC marine thematic node which are analysis-ready for EDITO and EOSC purposes</p>			
<p>Federation of EDITO and EOSC catalogues of data resources.</p>	<p>MOi, CNR</p>	<p>By Dec 2028</p>	<p>Refined high-level governance considerations agreed with regard to federated access and resource onboarding.</p>
<p>Configure and deploy data spaces (metadata catalogues) for selected marine and climate data repositories.</p>	<p>MARIS, IFREMER, MOI, VLIZ, NOC, CNR, EMBL, EMBRC</p>	<p>By Dec 2028</p>	<p>Robust, high-performance “data spaces” deployed in the Node for selected RIs, enabling scalable access to large volumes of marine and climate observation data.</p>
<p>Develop uniform data access (client-side) and data provisioning (server-side) across catalogues and data spaces.</p>	<p>VLIZ, MARIS, IFREMER, MOI, CMCC</p>	<p>By June 2029</p>	<p>Seamless, technology-agnostic discovery and retrieval of marine and climate (metadata) datasets from catalogues and data spaces, including smart agents, with uniform client-side access layer (UDAL) and uniform server-side (OpenEO).</p>
<p>Making marine tailored application components available as service templates.</p>	<p>VLIZ, MARIS, AWI, ULiege, Ifremer, CMCC</p>	<p>By Jun 2029</p>	<p>Service templates deployed for a range of applications (DIVAnd, WebODV, EDITO STAC, Beacon, Galaxy, RStudio, MEI), linked to the Data Access services.</p>
<p>Strategic Action Path +APPLICATIONS: Trigger the development of innovative data analytics methods around priority environmental thematics to inspire and guide the community towards further evolving applications in support of key policy objectives.</p>			
<p>What</p>	<p>Who</p>	<p>When</p>	<p>KPI</p>

<p>A5. Develop and establish Thematic Services (Essential Ocean Variables) of importance for the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters and for validating the fitness of the Core, Generic, Data, and Exchange services of the EOSC marine thematic node</p>			
<p>Ecological Variables Biodiversity: Species composition, abundance, and distribution—tracking key taxa such as fish, molluscs, corals, seagrasses, and indicator/flagship species</p>	<p>IRD, FORTH, Ifremer</p>	<p>By Dec 2028</p>	<p>Visualisation services for fisheries data and fish stock assessment models available in EDITO by 2028</p>
<p>Oceanographic and Physical Variables Sea surface and subsurface <u>Temperature and Salinity</u> data</p>	<p>INGV, Ifremer, PokaPok, Oceanscope, MARIS</p>	<p>By Dec 2028</p>	<p>Operational pipeline for automated generation of EOVs/ECVs datasets in ARCO formats and derived products (i.e., Ocean Heat, Salt Content) available in EDITO by 2028</p>
<p>Pressure and Impact Variables: <u>Pollution Indicators:</u> Nutrients and Acidification</p>	<p>OGS, Ifremer, HCMR, ULiège, Pokapok, MARIS</p>	<p>By Dec 2028</p>	<p>Operational pipeline for automated generation of Eutrophication and Acidification indicators available in EDITO by 2028</p>
<p>Ecosystem Service and Socio-Economic Variables: <u>Carbon Sequestration:</u> Role of habitats in storing blue carbon; rates of sequestration, burial, and emissions</p>	<p>EMBL-EBI, ETHZ, MARIS</p>	<p>By Dec 2028</p>	<p>Thematic service integrating access to data from different national and international repositories, together with its analyses and interpretation, available in EDITO by 2028</p>
<p>Strategic Action Path +COMMUNITY: (Further) Grow a thriving ocean open science community, leveraging skills, incentives and rewards and promoting wide dissemination of FAIR methods incubated in the EOSC marine thematic node to boost innovation at a wider scale.</p>			
What	Who	When	KPI

A6. Promote the uptake of the Key Exploitable Results of the Blue-Cloud pilot and the Blue-Cloud 2026 projects by users of the EOSC marine thematic node and the wider EOSC community			
Promote the uptake of existing thematic services	ALL Partners	By Dec 2027	+5000 registered users across existing V Labs by Aug 2029
Expose the current catalogue of thematic services to the EOSC Federation and the EOSC Association in relevant meetings and events	CNR-ISTI, Trust-IT, Ifremer, EGI, SSBE, IRD, INGV, FORTH, OGS, CMCC, IEEE, EMBRC	By Dec 2027	+5000 registered users across existing V Labs by Aug 2029
Connect with other EOSC nodes to explore cross-exploitation and collaboration opportunities	EMBL-EBI, ETHZ, CNR-ISTI, MARIS	By Dec 2027	Collaboration established with at least 3 other EOSC candidate nodes
A7. Communicate, to disseminate, and to exploit the capabilities, results & outputs of the EOSC marine thematic node by wide engagement, including training			
Promoting clarity and transparency in the landscape for the EOSC community with regard to the role of this node vis a vis EDITO	SSBE, MOi, VLIZ, Trust-IT, CNR	By Jan 2027	+500 stakeholders informed via factsheet co-developed and co-promoted with EDITO
Set-up a training and support programme for capacity building for the EOSC marine thematic node users and stakeholders	VLIZ, Trust-IT, IEEE, MARIS, CNR, iFremer, OGS, HCMR, ULiège, IRD, FORTH, CMCC, ETHZ, EBI, SSBE	By Jan 2027	+300 participants engaged in dissemination and training activities by Aug 2029

Strategic Action Path +ALLIANCES: Connect and align with wider developments and other communities to contribute to a European and a global, international knowledge system in support of the Ocean Pact, the EU Green Deal and the UN Agenda 2030.

What	Who	When	KPI
A8. Formulate and establish the governance structure and sustainability plan for the EOSC marine thematic node in the context of the EDITO and EOSC programs.			
Establish a dialogue and conditions for federated technical governance within EOSC	CNR, MOi, VLIZ, Trust-IT, Ifremer, SSBE	By Dec 2027	Working group established
Establish the EDITO-EOSC node governance scheme and sustainability plan	SSBE, MOi, VLIZ, CNR	By Dec 2028	Governance scheme published
A9. Connect with relevant developments and actions of the Decade Ocean Science for Sustainable Developments, exposing EDITO and the thematic node to international users and contributing to international cooperation in support of the Ocean Decade challenges, with a special focus on Challenge 8 “Create a digital representation of the ocean”			
Broaden the planned training and support programme for capacity building for the EOSC marine thematic node and EDITO users and stakeholders to engage international participants	SSBE, MOi, VLIZ, CNR	By Dec 2027	+250 international participants engaged in dissemination and training activities by Aug 2029

6 Pathways towards sustainability

The sustainability of Blue-Cloud 2026's results and of the emerging EOSC Node is defined by an evolutionary path from a pilot Research & Innovation (R&I) initiative to a permanent, operational component of the European marine data landscape. This transition ensures that the federated ecosystem developed for oceans and waters is integrated into the official **EOSC Federation** and the **European Digital Twin Ocean**.

The journey begins with the **Blue-Cloud 2026 Virtual Research Environment (VRE)**, powered by the D4Science platform, which has successfully piloted a "candidate" marine thematic node, as explained in Sections 1, 3 and 4 of this document. The strategic goal is now to formalize this into the **EOSC Node "European Digital Twin Ocean"**, serving as the official thematic entry point for the marine community within the wider EOSC ecosystem.

To achieve a cohesive digital environment for the **EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030**, a "Smart Federation" is required between the established Blue-Cloud VRE and the **EDITO** public core infrastructure. This federation ensures the mutual exposure of analytical processes, allowing researchers to build and run complex, data-intensive workflows across both platforms seamlessly. A newly funded project -namely "**EOSC-Marine: Operationalizing the EOSC Node | European Digital Twin Ocean to Support the EU Mission Ocean & Waters**" (Horizon Europe project 101292903 funded by REA under the Call HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01) will serve as the R&I vehicle to implement this integration. Coordinated by CNR, this project is tasked with the research activities required to embed the EOSC Node into the overall EDITO infrastructure, and with the implementation of the Action Plan 2026-2028 described in Section 5.

While the "EOSC Marine" project drives the research, the **EDITO** program will provide the mechanism for long-term operationalization. This phase requires that the European Digital Twin Ocean becomes a fully operational public service by 2030. Within this framework, **CNR** is specifically tasked with:

- **Node Deployment:** Establishing the EOSC Node Digital Twin Ocean within the public EDITO core, leveraging the methodological developments from Blue-Cloud and the EOSC Ocean & Waters project.
- **Scaling & Performance:** Scaling up Cloud and HPC services to support complex, high-resolution oceanographic modeling and AI-driven analysis.
- **Pre-operational Services:** Establishing automated operational pipelines to prevent the obsolescence of tools and validating "quality-labeled" applications for critical marine management areas such as fisheries, biodiversity, and Marine Spatial Planning.

By splitting these efforts between a dedicated R&I project ("**EOSC Marine**") for technical integration and a public infrastructure action ("**European Digital Twin Ocean - EDITO**") for operational scaling, the sustainability of Blue-Cloud's legacy as an EOSC marine thematic node is secured as a cornerstone of the future European Digital Twin Ocean.

7 Recommendations

The successful implementation of this roadmap will require the collaboration and support of a broad range of actors who are key in funding and/or shaping the marine knowledge value chain, as well as other actors of the wider research and data landscape, towards the well-coordinated and articulated European research and innovation data space aimed by EOSC. Table 3 gathers a set of recommendations for selected, target actors that are considered relevant to realise the full potential of the Node, paving the way for the successful delivery of its vision and mission.

Table 3: Recommendations to key EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean” stakeholders

Recommendations to	Recommendation	When
EU Policy Officers (funders)	1. Propose the inclusion of the EOSC node “European Digital Twin Ocean” in the EDITO program, to secure the availability of financial resources to sustainably fund its operations as an operational service delivered to EOSC users in the framework of said program.	2026-2029
	2. Activate measures to ensure that the core infrastructure and technologies supporting the EOSC node “European Digital Twin Ocean” and its public services are open-source and based on generally adopted standards.	2026-2029
	3. Actively participate in the governance of the new EOSC node to support alignment with EDITO governance, EOSC governance, and EU policy strategies and objectives.	2026-2029
	4. Continue fostering, enabling and supporting cross-DG communication within the European Commission to provide clarity for the community of the positioning of EOSC marine thematic node vis a vis EDITO.	2026-2029
Marine researchers, (data) scientists, developers and innovators (users)	5. Support the co-creation of the EOSC marine thematic node by testing EDITO’s capabilities and contributing feedback to inform and prioritize the EDITO-D4science interoperability roadmap on existing services.	2026-2029
	6. Actively participate in the definition of the governance of the new EOSC node and plan to actively participate in such governance to ensure that it is continuously shaped and improved to respond to the needs of users.	2026-2029

"EOSC Marine" project Consortium Partners	7. Endorse this Strategic Roadmap as providing the founding principles and priorities that will guide the development of the EOSC Node "European Digital Twin Ocean".	May 2026
	8. Communicate a clear vision to external audiences: Ensure that any external communications contribute to clarify and not confuse the marine knowledge community with regard to the intended direction of the node, which is to contribute to bridge EDITO and EOSC, ensuring a unified, single environment servicing users.	2026-2029
EDITO2 Implementing Partners	9. Support the ambition and plans of the European Commission for the further evolution of the European Open Science Cloud as a data space for research by facilitating efforts to make EDITO fully interoperable with EOSC using recognized, international standards in the deployment of the EDITO infrastructure and services.	2026-2029
Marine Research Infrastructures	10. Ensure that data pipelines from Research Infrastructures to EMODnet and/or EDITO, are appropriate, established, robust, maintained, sustainable, and technically integrated, so that RI data can be discovered and harnessed in the EOSC Node "European Digital Twin Ocean" by a large user base of multidisciplinary users.	2026-2029
Relevant, related bodies within the EOSC Federation, including the EOSC Association, the Nodes Operational Committee and/or dedicated working groups addressing data, as appropriate	11. Take note of this Strategic Roadmap as providing the founding principles and priorities that will guide the development of the EOSC Node "European Digital Twin Ocean".	May 2026
	12. Contribute to promote the generic services offered by the EOSC Node "European Digital Twin Ocean" and encourage their uptake by other (candidate) nodes.	2026-2029
	13. Take note that EDITO will be making data available in EOSC via EMODnet and Copernicus Marine Service data catalogues, which follow international (OGC, STAC) standards. EOSC can harvest their full catalogue specification, so anyone in EOSC can access this public, open data. If EOSC wishes to place the EDITO catalogue into the EOSC catalogue, EOSC should connect to EDITO's STAC catalogue and harvest it, rather than making these services adapt to internal standards.	2026-2029
Destination Earth and EDITO	14. Share plans for interoperability with EOSC to align a common roadmap for collaboration and interoperability between DestinE and EDITO on EOSC.	2026-2029

EU Green Deal Data Space	15. Take note of this Strategic Roadmap as providing the founding principles and priorities that will guide the development of the EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean”, as a marine component of the EOSC data space.	2026-2029
Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development - Decade Coordination Office for Data Sharing	16. Take note of progress achieved by Blue-Cloud 2026 scientific partners in combining data from different (international) sources (e.g., World Ocean Data Base, Copernicus Marine, EMODnet) to develop data products (EOVs) that can inform progress on specific Sustainable Development Goals and help promote these services for uptake by a wider, global user base.	May 2026
	17. Consider uptake of (selected) thematic services and/or related data products offered by the EOSC thematic node for exploitation in digital products being developed in the framework of the Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (e.g., the Digital Atlas).	2026-2029

8 Conclusions

The Horizon Europe “Blue-Cloud 2026” project is on track to successfully evolve its Key Exploitable Results from outcomes of a Research & Innovation Action into structural, long-term components of the marine knowledge value chain. The infrastructure and digital ecosystem that shapes, underpins and/or gives cohesion to these results is planned to become fully interoperable and seamlessly integrated in **EDITO** (<https://www.edito.eu/>), the public infrastructure of the **European Digital Twin Ocean**, and to evolve as an **EOOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean”** that contributes to bridge EDITO and EOOSC. This new EOOSC Node will champion a vision where major EU marine knowledge assets (i.e. EMODnet, Copernicus Marine, EDITO), and environmental and marine Research Infrastructures (from ESFRI and beyond) are central to driving marine data provision in EOOSC, supporting and catalysing open science developments in the marine and freshwater domains. The Node will:

- Ensure that the **EDITO** platform, catalogue and services (<https://www.edito.eu/>) are fully accessible and integrated within EOOSC, including by influencing EOOSC requirements to avoid unnecessary duplication of efforts by encouraging the adoption of international, open standards by the EOOSC Federation.
- Support scientists and researchers in designing, testing, and evaluating innovative computational analytical flows that extract valuable knowledge from diverse datasets, while accelerating open science and collaborative research in support of the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters”.
- Offer a comprehensive environment for sharing data, tools, and knowledge, fostering a "web of scientific insight" that supports the federation of relevant marine and aquatic data sources for discovery by the entire EOOSC community, fostering their ingestion into EDITO (including via relevant, existing services i.e., EMODnet) towards nurturing and co-evolving the European Digital Twin Ocean.

Bringing this vision forward will require additional work at technical, operational and strategic level, including agreement on the governance scheme that will ensure that the vision and mission of the EOOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean” is delivered according to this plan, and/or evolved further to adapt to future changes in the marine knowledge and research landscape, if/as needed. To this end, an implementation roadmap has been envisioned, covering three distinctive phases:

- **Phase 1 (Sep 2026 - Aug 2029):** Set up - from candidate to production.
- **Phase 2 (Sep 2029 - Dec 2030):** Operations at EOOSC level.
- **Phase 3 (Jan 2031- Dec 2035):** Service Sustainability, Governance and Scale Up.

By 2035, the aim is to deliver the EOOSC thematic node as an operational service in the framework of the EDITO program that accelerates the co-creation and further expansion of the European Digital Twin Ocean by facilitating multidisciplinary research collaboration across EOOSC, and onboarding of valuable, community validated digital assets onto EDITO, via wider user and stakeholder engagement. The Action Plan 2026-2029 outlines the key milestones that will guide progress towards this strategic objective in the first phase of this roadmap. Activities in this period will be funded by the action “**EOOSC-Marine:**

Operationalizing the EOSC Node | European Digital Twin Ocean to Support the EU Mission Ocean & Waters (EOSC-Marine)” (Horizon Europe project 101292903 funded by REA).

As previously mentioned, the successful implementation of this Strategic Roadmap and related future Action Plans will require alignment across a wide range of stakeholders, well beyond the “Blue-Cloud 2026” and “EOSC-Marine” consortium Partners. Initial feedback gathered through stakeholder consultations undertaken during the Blue-Cloud 2026 project included recommendations to consortium Partners to contribute to strengthen and not fragment existing European marine knowledge services, community and value chain via the new Node; to communicate a clear vision to external audiences that contribute to clarify and not confuse the marine knowledge community with regard to the intended direction of the Node, which is to contribute to bridging EDITO and EOSC, ensuring a unified, single environment servicing users; and to avoid vendor lock-in when implementing technologies, making sure that the EOSC Node is driven by open-source technologies. Additional recommendations for both internal and external stakeholders have been further outlined in this Strategic Roadmap, including for funders (EC representatives), “Blue-Cloud 2026” and “EOSC Marine” consortium Partners, marine researchers, marine research infrastructures, EDITO2 implementing Partners, the EOSC Association, EDITO, DestinE, the EU Green Deal Data Space and the Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development. These stakeholders will be contacted and invited to take note of the contents of this Strategic Roadmap, and to consider following through on the specific recommendations targeted to each actor, respectively and as relevant. Further exchanges will be systematically planned via stakeholder engagement channels set up towards that end as part of the “EOSC Marine” action (2026-2029) and beyond, via new governance envisioned.

The implementation of this Strategic Roadmap will pave the way to the successful development and integration of a federated digital ecosystem in support of Mission “Ocean & Waters” into EOSC, and to its operationalisation as a long-term component of the EDITO program.

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10 Annex: Blue-Cloud 2026 services to be integrated as part of the EO SC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean” offering

10.1 Graphic overview of core and thematic services offered by Blue-Cloud 2026

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A federated European FAIR and Open Research Ecosystem for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters

Scan the QR Code to visit our website blue-cloud.org

Core services: Virtual Research environment
 An Open Science platform for collaborative marine research, using a wide variety of datasets and analytical tools, complemented by generic services such as sub-setting, pre-processing, harmonising, publishing and visualisation. The VRE hosts different Virtual Labs and is going to include thematic Workbenches, which users can access with existing credentials in EO SC, the European Open Science Cloud. The Blue-Cloud Marine Node implements several core capabilities, as defined by the EO SC Federation Handbook, to ensure effective operation and service deliver such as the Catalogue, AAI, the Gateway and more.

Generic services

- Workspace
- RStudio
- JupyterHub
- Galaxy
- CCP services

Data management facilities

- NoSQL Database
- Relational Database
- DD&AS
- Beacon

Marine Thematic Services
 Virtual Labs offer data products and analytical tools within the Virtual Research Environment (VRE). These V Labs serve as real-life demonstrators for web-based open science and are available for testing by research communities within the EO SC Federation. The V Labs offer applications for data processing, publishing data results, and managing computation routines.

Vlabs

- Coastal Ocean Observations along Europe**: This VLab enables access, integration and use of observations from European coastal ocean areas. By combining JERICO-RI and complementary data with advanced processing, analytical tools and interactive visualisations, it offers deeper insight into key coastal processes.
- Coastal currents from observations**: This VLab generates integrated ocean surface current maps from HF radar, drifters and altimetry data using the DIVIND method. It merges these datasets with constraints such as coastline presence, horizontal divergence and momentum balance between acceleration, Coriolis force and surface pressure gradient.
- Carbon Reservoir Dynamics**: This VLab analyses the relative contribution of drivers in phytoplankton dynamics in the Benelux North Sea and northern Adriatic Sea. Using an NPZD model based on plankton, nutrient and carbon data, it explores spatio-temporal variations and assesses whether these systems act as a carbon sink or source.
- Marine Environmental Indicators**: The Marine Environmental Indicators (MEI) VLab enables users to monitor and assess the environmental status of marine areas to support ocean management decisions. It performs online spatio-temporal analysis of selected environmental variables using implemented algorithms.
- Global Fisheries Atlas**: The “Global Fisheries Atlas” VLab aims to provide a comprehensive view of global fisheries to support informed decision-making and resource management. Its two main pillars are the Fisheries Atlas and the Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries.

Workbenches

- Physics: temperature & salinity**: This Workbench will implement a cloud based workflow to generate harmonised, validated and customisable EO V data collections for temperature and salinity, integrating datasets released from different EU and non-EU data infrastructures for the test region of the Mediterranean Sea.
- Eutrophication: chlorophyll, nutrients, oxygen**: This Workbench will define and implement an efficient production workflow to merge multi-source datasets managed by Copernicus Marine Service, EMODnet Chemistry and the World Ocean Database, together with key EU RIs and build highly qualified EO V datasets for eutrophication variables: chlorophyll, nutrients, oxygen.
- Ecosystem-level EO Vs**: The Ecosystem Workbench aims to improve the availability, quality, and interoperability of large collections of plankton observations and extrapolated biogeographies. This habitat modeling workflow will generate high-quality interpolated maps of these plankton entities, at the global scale and produce ecosystem-level EO Vs.

Funded by the European Union

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Figure 5: Overview of Blue-Cloud 2026 core and thematic services

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10.2 Graphic overview of thematic services offered by Blue-Cloud 2026

Virtual Laboratories in the Blue-Cloud VRE

Operational science environments on D4Science for marine observations, modelling, indicators and fisheries knowledge services

How to use the VLABs

User handbooks
Released in January 2025 (beta) and January 2026 (latest version).

Gateway access
Users first create an account on the Blue-Cloud 2026 Gateway; the first section of the handbook explains the steps.

Training
A dedicated OTGA self-paced course has been developed for each VLab to help users work with the services and outputs.

Links & QR codes
URLs / QR codes for the Gateway, handbooks, VLab pages and course pages.

VLab 1 | Integration of Coastal Ocean Observations along Europe (ICOOE)

Coastal observations platform integrating JERICO-RI and other European Blue Data Infrastructures.

- Integrates coastal observations to study connectivity, contaminants, river outflows, extreme events and repeated glider sections.
- Offers dashboards, data reporting, QC/pre-processing, trajectory analyses, current-field statistics and glider processing/viewing tools.

Thematic services address transboundary transport, extreme events and ocean-glider added value.

Partners:

At a glance

All VLABs are running on D4Science in the Blue-Cloud VRE.

- Virtual Laboratories
- User handbooks (Jan 2025, Jan 2026)
- Blue-Cloud Gateway account required (for free)
- OTGA self-paced training pathways

Conference-ready link panel

D4Science Gateway

D4 VLABs Handbook V2

Virtual Labs 2026

VLab 2 course

VLab 3 course

VLab 5 course

VLab 2 | Coastal Currents from Observations

Integrated surface current maps from HF radar, drifters and satellite altimetry using DIVAnd.

- Produces gridded NetCDF surface-current maps by merging HF radar, drifters and altimetry over coastal regions.
- Uses optimisation and validation against independent drifters, then supports Lagrangian trajectories and oil-spill simulations.

Partners:

VLab 3 | Carbon-Plankton Dynamics

NPZD modelling in carbon units for plankton dynamics and carbon-flow simulations.

- Simulates nutrients, phytoplankton, zooplankton and detritus while tracking carbon flows.
- Provides Jupyter notebooks and an interactive RShiny app using SST, salinity, nutrients, pCO₂, wind and pH forcing.

Partners:

Access, training and portfolio overview

The project produced five domain-focused VLABs. Each combines data access, analysis services and reproducible workflows, while the handbooks and Ocean Teacher Global Academy courses support onboarding and re-use.

- Register on the Blue-Cloud 2026 Gateway before accessing services.
- Handbooks document data sources, how-to workflows and options to include additional data.
- Each VLab is paired with a self-paced OTGA training course.

VLab 1 ICOOE
VLab 2 Coastal Currents
VLab 3 Carbon-Plankton

VLab 4 Indicators
VLab 5 Fisheries Atlas

VLab themes

Observation integration
ICOOE unifies coastal observations and thematic services for connectivity, storms and gliders.

Surface current reconstruction
Coastal Currents from Observations merges HF radar, drifters and altimetry using DIVAnd.

Ecosystem and carbon modelling
Carbon-Plankton Dynamics provides NPZD simulations in carbon units.

Environmental indicators + Fisheries knowledge
MEI supports ocean management.

Fisheries Global Atlas
GFA harmonises fisheries data and knowledge products.

VLab 4 | Marine Environmental Indicators

Unified indicator workflows for marine environmental assessment and decision support.

- Computes Marine Heatwaves, Ocean Heat Content, TRIX eutrophication and Storm Severity Index v2 via notebooks and a dedicated web application.
- Produces maps, time series and downloadable outputs, with job handling through the VRE Analytics Engine and Cloud Computing Platform.

A video tutorial is available on the Blue-Cloud YouTube channel.

Partners:

VLab 5 | Global Fisheries Atlas

Global fisheries knowledge and data services built from authoritative sources.

- Harmonises fisheries data and knowledge sources for graphical interfaces and programmatic access.
- Combines GRSF knowledge services with Global Tuna Atlas workflows, dashboards and web mapping, supported by GitHub, Zenodo DOIs and RStudio/CI environments.

Partners:

Contributing teams acknowledged in the source text

VLab 1: Instituto Hidrográfico, SOCI, IEEE
VLab 2: Université de Liège, CMCC Foundation
VLab 3: Flanders Marine Institute, VLIZ, National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics - OGS
VLab 4: CMCC, INGV, OGS, KNMI, Nubisware
VLab 5: IRI, FORTH, FAO and tuna RIFMO / FIRMS data managers

eOSC | Blue-Cloud2026 + D4SCIENCE

Five VLABs, two handbooks and a complete training path for marine research communities.

Reproducible science services
Gateway onboarding
Self-paced learning

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Figure 6: Blue-Cloud 2026 Virtual Laboratories

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EUTROPHICATION WORKBENCH:

Advancing harmonisation, standardization and big-data workflows for eutrophication EOVs in marine science.

Nydia Catalina Reyes Suarez, Alessandra Giorgetti, Julie Gatti, Virginie Racape, Karin Westlander, Athanasia (Sissy) Iona, Lotta Fyrbjerg, Megan Anne French, Robin Kooyman, Gwenaëlle Moncoiffe, Maxence Couppez, Alban Sizun and Marine Vernet.

Learn more about this Workbench

Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) are critical for ocean monitoring and policy, yet remain fragmented across infrastructures such as EMODnet, Copernicus, and the World Ocean Database (WOD), limiting interoperability and reuse. Blue-Cloud 2026 addresses this challenge through cloud-based workbenches built on the D4Science infrastructure, enabling the harmonisation and integration of large marine datasets. The eutrophication workbench combines multi-source data using BEACON, supports exploration via webODV, and applies dedicated tools (CWdt, File Forge) for duplicate detection and handling. This approach delivers scalable, reproducible workflows and high-quality, harmonised and standardized EOVS datasets in biogeochemistry, supporting eutrophication assessment in European and global initiatives such as the EDITO, EOVS, SDG 14, MSFD, and the EU Mission Ocean and Waters.

Blue data infrastructures

STEPS

1

2

3

EOV selection

- Chlorophylla
- Dissolved Oxygen
- Nutrients (nitrate, nitrite-nitrate, ammonium, phosphate, and silicate)

Beacon

- Semantic harmonization
- data and metadata standardisation
- Efficient access to multidimensional data
- Different output formats

Monolithic BEACON instances

- BEACON @ EMODnet Chemistry
- BEACON @ Copernicus BCC
- BEACON @ WOD

Merged BEACON instance (workbench core)

Merged BEACON Eutrophication Instance

Query harmonized and standardized, multi-source EOVS collection in volume or mass units for any Eutrophication EOVS (chlorophylla, nutrients and oxygen)

EWB User workflow

USER INPUTS

MASTER SETUP NOTEBOOK (Automated)

DATA EXTRACTION from BEACON (SuppyLab)

DUPLICATE DETECTION (CWduplicates-tool) (CCP)

FILEFORGE CLEANING & CONVERSION (CCP)

IMPORT & QC (webODV) (Manual)

EXECUTION ENVIRONMENTS

FILE FLOW SUMMARY

Developed in collaboration with:

Watch the Interview!

Scan to visit the EWB VLab

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Adobe Acrobat

Figure 7: Blue-Cloud 2026 Eutrophication Workbench

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Funded by the European Union

Blue-Cloud 2026 – A federated European FAIR and Open Research Ecosystem for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe programme under Grant Agreement no. 101094227

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EPHALOPOD ETH zürich AtlantECO BITOcean5D

CEPHALOPOD: a standardized and flexible framework for marine habitat modelling across data types and sources

Alexandre Schicckel^{1*}, Corentin Clerc^{1*}, Fabio Benedetti¹, Jean-Olivier Irissou¹, Matthias Münnich¹, Meike Vogt¹
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^{*}equally contributed to this poster

Abstract

Here, we introduce the Cloud-based Ensemble Pipeline for Habitat modelling Across Large-scale Ocean Plankton Observation Datasets (CEPHALOPOD). Through two example of applications, we illustrate the framework ability to extrapolate plankton distributions in space and time based on traditional net observations or omics datasets. CEPHALOPOD addresses to a broad spectrum of stakeholders, including researchers, policymakers, conservationists, and educational institutions.

Evaluate zooplankton global biomass and distribution

Pipeline input: biomass retrieved from traditional net zooplankton observations*
Pipeline output: extrapolated spatio-temporal PFT-resolved plankton distribution
Applications: Earth System Model evaluation (PFT-specific), global plankton ecology (trophic pyramid, size spectrum, traits biogeography)

Visualizing EOVs and EBVs with CEPHALOView

ACCESS CEPHALOView
<https://bryout.com/cephaloview>

LEARN MORE ABOUT THIS WORKBENCH

WATCH THE INTERVIEW!

Matt

Alexandre

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Figure 8: Blue-Cloud 2026 Biodiversity Workbench

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